

Spack Cheat Sheet

Directories

\$tmpdir/\$user/spack-stage Built packages
\$spack/var/spack/cache Source files
\$spack/etc/spack/defaults/config.yaml Default configuration
\$home/.spack/packages.yaml External packages

The environment variable \$user is your username (moniker) and \$tmpdir is the default temporary directory (usually tmp). the default temporary directory can be changed by setting \$TMP or \$TMPDIR.

spack clean --stage Clean compiled packages
spack clean -a

Installation and activation

```
1 # Install Spack
2 git clone --depth=2
3   https://github.com/spack/spack.git
4 # Activate Spack
5 . ./spack/share/spack/setup-env.sh
6 # Run spack
7 spack
```

Please use -b v1.0.1 to clone a specific release. If you use a different shell and not bash change setup-env.sh to your favorite bash.

Updating the build in packages

The built in packages are located here
<https://github.com/spack/spack-packages>.

```
1 # pull the latest packages
2 spack repo update
3 # pull a specific commit
4 spack repo update --commit 2bf4ab9585 builtin
```

Installation

spack install <name> Install package <name>
spack install -j n Number of n parallel jobs
spack install -v Verbose build output
spack install --no-cache Do not use cache
spack -v verbose output
spack -debug Debug output

To install a specific version of the package we use spack install wget@1.17 and to install a package with a specific compiler we use spack install wget %gcc@12.2.0. To specify the version and the compiler, we use spack install wget@1.17 %gcc@13.2.0.

Loading and deleting packages

spack load <name> Load package <name>
spack load <name>@<version> Load package by <version>
spack load /<hash> load package by <hash>
spack info <name> List available versions
spack list <name> List packages
spack delte <name> Delete package
spack gc Garbage collection

Adding compilers

spack compilers List all compilers
spack compiler find FInd new compilers
spack compiler info <name> Shows info
If your favorite compiler is not available use
spack install gcc@13.2.0 or install spack install llvm@17 to install it. That takes a while and you might want to get a hot beverage ☕.

Adding external packages

spack external find openmpi Search for openmpi
spack external find mpich Search for mpich
spack external find cuda Search for CUDA
spack external find <name> Search for package <name>
You can try to add system packages using
spack external find python or external find openssl. Spack will use these packages and that can reduce the compilation time. Note that finding MPI packages us currently broken in Spack 1.0.

Concretization

spack install kokkos@4.4 Install version 4.4.
spack install kokkos%gcc@12 Compile with gcc 12.
spack install kokkos +openmp Compile OpenMP backend
spack install kokkos ~openmp Do not compile OpenMP
spack install kokkos ^cuda@12.4.1 Use CUDA 12.4.1
To build Kokkos 4.4 with CUDA support using CUDA 12.4.1 support with gcc 12.2.0 we could use
spack install kokkos@4.4 +cuda cuda_arch=80 %gcc@12.2.0 ^cuda@12.4.1. To list all available variants, we use
spack info <name>.

```
1 spack info hdf5
2 Variants:
3   cxx [false] false, true
4   Enable C++ support
5   fortran [false] false, true
6   Enable Fortran support
7   mpi [true] false, true
8   Enable MPI support
```

We observe that the package hdf5 is build as default
spack install hdf5 ~cxx ~fortran +mpi. The dependencies (∧) are listed as well.

```
1 Build Dependencies:
2   cmake gmake java mpi mpich ninja
3   szip zlib-api
4 Link Dependencies:
5   mpi mpich szip zlib-api
```

To build the package with a specific version of CMake we can use spack install hdf5 ^cmake@3.18.

Environments

If a environment is activated all packages installed or deleted are related to the environment and have no effect on other environment or the global spack installation.

spack env create <name> Create env <name>
spack env activate <name> Activate env <name>
spack env deactivate Deactivate current env
spack -e <env> install kokkos Install kokkos in env

Create a named environment 😊

```
1 spack env activate -p foo
2 [foo] [diehlpk@darwin-fe1 ~]$
```

Show the activated environment 😊

```
1 spack env status
2 ==> In environment foo
```

Anonymous environments

```
1 # Creating an anonymous environment
2 spack env create --dir my_env
3 spack env create ./my_env
4 # Activate anonymous environment
5 spack env activate ./ my_env
```

Development builds

Spack will install all dependencies and run cmake to configure Kokkos but will not build Kokkos.

```
1 git clone https://github.com/kokkos/kokkos.git
2 cd kokkos
3 spack dev-build --fresh --drop-in bash \
4   --until cmake kokkos@4.4 +cuda ^cuda@12.4.1 +op
5 cd spack-build
6 make -j 8
```

Note for development build need a specific version and Spack will not use the default one.
For more details about Spack, please head to spack.readthedocs.org.